

Configuration of Aldoximes by Conductivity

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Manuscript received 20 September 1982, revised 18 April 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

Conductivities of a few pairs of *syn*- and *anti*-aldoximes and some salicylaldoxime were determined in 40% dimethylformamide. *Anti*-aldoximes gave higher molecular conductance as compared to the *syn*-aldoximes.

SOME early workers¹ observed conductivities of sodium salts of isomeric aldoximes in aqueous solutions and determined indirectly the dissociation constant (K_a) of the aldoximes. They observed that the *syn*-aldoximes have higher dissociation constants than the *anti* forms. Perhaps, they had used the older notations.

Patwardhan and Deshpande measured the conductivity of aldoximes directly on the two isomers in liquid sulphur dioxide². They observed that the *anti* form in all cases gave a higher conductance than the *syn*-oxime.

Compared to liquid sulphur dioxide dimethylformamide (DMF) is found to be a better conducting media. Therefore, conductivities of a few pairs of *syn*- and *anti*-aldoximes and some salicylaldoximes have been determined in DMF.

Experimental

Conductivity was measured with NAINA digital conductivity meter, type NDC 732 at $24 \pm 1^\circ$ using Philips conductivity cell capacity 40.0 ml. The solution was covered with a three hole lid to accommodate a burette, the electrodes and a thermometer and was stirred with a magnetic stirrer. The specific conductivity was directly recorded from the digital conductivity meter. A number of measurements were taken at different dilutions of the aldoximes.

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. The oximes were prepared generally by reacting the respective aldehydes with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and caustic soda. Some of the *anti* forms were prepared by passing dry HCl gas through the ethereal solution of the *syn* form. The special conditions mentioned in the literature were followed according to the references given in Table 1.

The specific conductivities of the oximes were determined by subtracting the specific conductivity of 40% dimethylformamide solution from the observed specific conductivity of aldoximes in

TABLE 1

Aldoxime	<i>Syn</i> form	m.p. °C Obs. (Lit)	<i>Anti</i> form	m.p. °C Obs. (Lit)
1. Furfuraldoxime	Brady and Goldstein ³	74 (74)	Brady and Goldstein ³	92 (92)
2. <i>p</i> -Chloro benzaldoxime	Beilstein ⁴	105 (106)	Beilstein ⁴	142 (142)
3. Salicylaldoxime	Vogel ⁵	57 (57)	—	—
4. 5-Chloro salicylaldoxime	Willey and Wakefield ⁶	128 (128)	—	—
5. 5-Bromo salicylaldoxime	Pandya and Pandya ⁷	125 (126)	—	—
6. 3,5-Dibromo salicylaldoxime	Wentworth and Brady ⁸	219 (218-20)	—	—

dimethylformamide. Molecular conductance (μ) was calculated by using the equation (i)

$$\mu = k \times v \dots (i)$$

where, k = specific conductance (mhos) and
 v = volume in ml containing 1 mole of the substance.

Results and Discussion

The results of conductivity measurements of the aldoximes are summarized in Table 2.

The molecular conductance of *syn* and *anti* forms of furfuraldoxime and *p*-chlorobenzaldoxime were determined under identical experimental conditions. It was observed that the *anti*-aldoximes gave higher molecular conductance as compared to the *syn*-aldoximes (Table 2.) This indicates that among the pairs of the oximes, the configuration of the *syn* and *anti* isomers could easily be decided. If, however, only one of the isomers is available, it is difficult to decide the configuration of the oxime by conductivity measurement.

Our observations are in agreement with those of Patwardhan and Deshpande (*loc.cit.*) who used liquid sulphur dioxide as the conducting media.

The oximes of salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde, obtainable only in single form, are

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TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENTS OF ALDOXIMES IN 40% DMF SOLUTION
 Sp. conductance of 40% DMF = 10×10^{-6} mhos; $t = 24 \pm 1^\circ$

Aldoximes	Oxime g/100 ml	Mole/lit	Sp. conductance (k) mhos $\times 10^6$	Mol. conductance (μ) mhos
1. <i>Syn</i> -furfuraldoxime	0.1110	0.01	8.0	0.8
	0.0555	0.005	4.0	0.8
2. <i>Anti</i> furfuraldoxime	0.1110	0.01	111.0	11.1
	0.0555	0.005	58.0	11.6
3. <i>Syn</i> - <i>p</i> -chloro benzaldoxime	0.1555	0.01	20.0	2.0
	0.0777	0.005	9.0	1.8
4. <i>Anti</i> - <i>p</i> -chloro benzaldoxime	0.1555	0.01	67.0	6.7
	0.0777	0.005	33.0	6.6
5. Salicylaldoxime	0.137	0.01	20.2	2.02
	0.0685	0.005	10.0	2.00
6. 5-Chloro salicylaldoxime	0.1715	0.01	14.2	1.45
	0.08575	0.005	7.2	1.44
7. 5-Bromo salicylaldoxime	0.216	0.01	11.25	1.125
	0.108	0.005	5.7	1.14
8. 3,5-Dibromo salicylaldoxime	0.295	0.01	28.6	2.86
	0.1475	0.005	14.2	2.84

known to form an intramolecular hydrogen bond. The molecular conductance of these hydrogen bonded oximes in 40% DMF solution did not show any regularity. These oximes have the structures (I), (II), (III) and (IV), respectively.

It is seen that 3,5-dibromosalicylaldoxime has a different hydrogen bonded structure as compared to (I), (II) and (III). Structure like (I) is not possible for 3,5-dibromosalicylaldoxime due to steric influence of the bromine atom at position 3. Due to strong electronegative character of the bromine atom, a five-membered hydrogen bonded structure is possible as is depicted in structure (IV).

It is observed that the molecular conductance of the *syn* forms of salicylaldoximes, 5-chlorosalicylaldoxime and 5-bromosalicylaldoxime are in decreasing order (Table 2), and it is difficult to make a

general statement based on these meagre experimental data.

On the basis of non-formation of the hydrochloride of 3,5-dibromosalicylaldoxime, Brady⁶ suggested that it possesses *syn* configuration. It is observed that the molecular conductance of 3,5-dibromosalicylaldoxime is 2.85 and it is not possible to judge the configuration on the basis of molecular conductance.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.B.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship.

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